

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Undersown crops in organic potato cultivation in Germany

This case study examines the effects of undersown crops specifically developed by Deutsche Saatveredelung AG (DSV) for potato cultivation. The seed mixture used consisted of 35% summer vetch, 25% flax, 21% perennial ryegrass, 10% ramtilia, and 9% Persian clover. These crops were sown using two different techniques: strip sowing and broad sowing. The aim of the study was to encourage soil fauna that feed on fungi in organic potato farming systems and to evaluate their potential to naturally control fungal diseases such as Fusarium and Alternaria, along with their harmful mycotoxins.

In the first year of the experiment (2021), three different treatments were applied. The first treatment (T1) served as the control and involved organic potato cultivation following the local farming practice, without any undersowing. The second treatment (T2) included strip undersowing, where the undersown crops were only planted in the furrows. The third treatment (T3) used broad undersowing, where the crops were planted both on the ridges and in the furrows. Apart from the

type of sowing, all other farming practices such as fertilization and soil preparation were the same across all treatments.

In the next two growing seasons (2022 and 2023), all the trial plots were managed using local farming practices. This setup made it possible to observe and assess the long-term effects of the treatments applied in 2021.

Tables

This table presents the average values of crop revenue, direct costs, and calculated gross margins for each crop cycle and the overall crop rotation. The revenue variability was impacted by the yields as those varied considerably across the cases. Due to huge variation in yield the gross margins for potato production varied significantly from 1,123 €/ha to 60 €/ha.

The direct costs were higher for fields with experimental treatment 2 (organic potato cultivation with broad undersowing).

	Costs (€/ha)	Revenues (€/ha)	Gross margin (€/ha)
T1: Control (Organic potato)	1,967	3,091	1,123
T2: Organic potato cultivation with strip undersowing	1,967	1,907	-60
T3: Organic potato cultivation with broad undersowing	1,978	2,058	80

1. Average value of production costs, sales revenues, and gross margins, calculated for each practice analysed in a 3-year rotation (potato-winter wheat-mustard).

KEYWORDS

Economic profitability, gross margin, undersown crops, potato cultivation

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